

Two Kinds of Equilibria: Wave and Particle/Dynamic Based?

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Classical statistical mechanics is often presented in terms of the maximization of entropy ($\ln(\# \text{ arrangements})$ or $\ln(\text{ total probability for a set of arrangements})$) subject to a constraint. In a previous note (1), we argued that such a process seems to be associated with a distributive variable which is a scalar i.e. is additive such that a product of probabilities $\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)$ of different values of this variable $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i = E$ is equivalent to a single probability of E i.e. $n(E)$. We applied this idea to both a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and a 3D random walk. This distributive variable changes in the stochastic process of the problem. For example for an MB gas, there are elastic collisions so energy is the distributive variable. For an MB gas in a potential $V(x)$, there is potential and kinetic energy of a single particle, but this is not regarded as a stochastic process in the classical view.

In (2) we argued that a distributed variable is not the only type of equilibrium which may exist, even in the classical world. We considered the example of a beam of light which reflects and refracts at $x=0$ (medium along the y axis). Energy is conserved even at the photon level, but there is an unknown probability namely that for reflection "a" because the refraction probability is then $1-a$. Thus energy conservation is not enough. We argued that in order to solve for this problem in an equilibrium or steady state manner, one needed to deal with square roots of fluxes/intensities in order to obtain two equations to solve for B, C i.e. square root fluxes at $x=0$ for the reflected and refracted rays in terms of A , the square root flux for the incident beam. We argued these fluxes were associated with eigenfunctions of the translation generator i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Thus a dynamic equilibrium is introduced (i.e. quantum mechanics) which does not use a distributed variable i.e. does not use maximization of entropy. Rather it is associated with eigenfunctions of the generator of the dynamical motion involved. It is this dynamical variable (e.g. p) which changes in this stochastic process even if in direction only.

A question arises: When does one use one type of equilibrium approach versus the other? We attempt to answer this in this note.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics is based on stochastic processes as opposed to the deterministic Newtonian mechanics. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, particles collide elastically. Thus energy is distributed and we call it a distributed variable. One may argue that momentum is also conserved, but energy conservation governs these collisions and it is an additive scalar. The statistical idea is then that the probability to have a certain amount of energy is the same whether it is distributed over one particle or several. If several are involved one has a product of probabilities i.e. an AND situation. Thus:

$$e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_3) = n(e_1)n(e_2) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1a)) and linking with ((1b)) yields the MB distribution $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where C and T are constants, the latter being called temperature. Given that momentum is also in the

picture, one may note that $e_i = \pi \cdot \pi / 2m$ and that there is a spherical shell with area proportional to $\pi \cdot \pi d|\pi|$ so this phase space factor may be multiplied with $\exp(-e_i/T)$. A similar distributed variable approach applies to a 3D random walk. We wish to point out that the distributed variable approach is identical to a maximization of entropy (ln of arrangements) view with a constraint which includes the distributed variable (not a function of it). In particular, the distributed variable approach as shown in ((1a)) and ((1b)) is of the form:

$$\ln(n(\text{distributed variable})) = -1/T \text{ distributed variable} \quad ((2))$$

$$((2)) \text{ may be rewritten as: } d/dn(e_i) \sum \text{over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) = -1/T \sum \text{over } i \ e_i n(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Where e_i is the distributed variable. ((2)), however, is of the form of a maximization problem with $\sum \text{over } i \ e_i n(e_i)$ being the constraint $n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$, however, matches Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(N!) \text{ approx} = N \ln(N) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Thus: } \sum \text{over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(e_i) \text{ approx} = N! / \text{Product } (n(e_i)N!) \quad ((5))$$

which is the number of arrangements for a given form of $n(e_i)$. Thus one sees a link between the distributed variable approach and maximization of entropy PROVIDED one use the constraint:

$$\text{Distributed variable } n(\text{distributed variable}) \quad ((6))$$

Thus one cannot use any constraint which may happen to be in the problem (even if it is a function of the distributed variable). As a result, this does not seem entirely like a free maximization subject to constraints in the problem.

In classical statistical mechanics, this seems to be the main approach used i.e. maximize entropy = ln(arrangements) subject to a constraint. We argued in (2), however, that a second equilibrium approach also exists for a physical phenomenon which is present in the classical world, namely the reflection and refraction of light.

Dynamical Equilibrium

Consider the problem of light moving in the positive x direction reflecting and refracting at the interface of a medium along the y axis at $x=0$. Even for a single photon, there is a probability to reflect "a" and $1-a$ to refract, but energy is conserved. Thus energy is not a distributed variable where the reflection/refraction represents the stochastic process. Using $E=pc$ one sees that p_1 (reflection) and p_2 (refraction) are not the same, but these are dynamical vectors and are not really associated with a distribution variable because the energy associated with both is the same. As a result, the distributed variable approach does not seem to work here. In fact, one may write a conservation of energy equation in terms of intensities (following (3)) i.e.

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((7)) \text{ where } AA \text{ simply indicates that intensity is strictly positive}$$

In this steady state problem, there is no distributed variable, but there are two unknowns B,C in terms of A and only one equation. In (2) we noted that one may write ((7)) in terms of two equations, one of which uses the dynamical variable and the other which provides a continuity of square root flux i.e.

$$A+B=C \text{ and } pA - pB = p^2C \quad ((8))$$

((8)) allows one to solve for B,C in terms of A and demonstrates a new kind of statistical mechanics/equilibrium/steady state namely one based on a dynamical quantity i.e. square root flux. We argued that this problem is linked to spatial invariance and that $\exp(ipx)$ is the eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ where d/dx is the translation generator. Thus this new statistical mechanics is based on the eigenfunctions of a generator linked to a particular type of dynamics, in this case translation along the x axis with p being the dynamical variable.

As argued in (1), there is no distributed variable here and so no maximization of entropy subject to the dynamical variable in the constraint.

We suggest that the above example which pertains to light also applies to quantum particles such as electrons, nucleons etc. We then consider another example, namely a quantum bound state, in which these dynamical probabilities appear.

Dynamical Probabilities and Quantum Bound States

Newtonian mechanics already treats a bound classical particle in a potential in a nonstochastic manner i.e. one has $x(t)$ with velocity and acceleration being given by various d/dt 's. In the above section we suggested that light and also a quantum particle are linked with $\exp(ipx)$, the eigenfunction of the generator associated with the dynamical motion which changes in the stochastic proces. In this expression \hbar/p represents a wavelength. If the wavelength is of the same order as the length of the bound region, one may expect the form $\exp(ipx)$ to be important. If \hbar/p is almost 0 one might not expect it to have much of an effect and would use Newton's approach. $\exp(ipx)$ represents a constant p, but Newton's approach indicates that p changes at each x. Thus one may suggest a stochastic process in which $V(x)$ delivers impulse hits to momentum. Thus the stochastic problem does not deal with a distributed variable, but rather with momentum, a dynamic one. One may note, however, that $E-V(x)$ is the kinetic energy available at each x point. A main idea, however, is that this energy is not distributed because the equilibrium is a dynamic one created by $V(x)$ delivering impulse hits to the various $\exp(ipx)$ s. Thus $E-V(x)$ as kinetic energy available at x serves only as a constraint. As a result we suggest that a bound state follows:

$$\left\{ \sum_{p} p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} = E-V(x) \quad ((9))$$

Thus ((9)) is a dynamical probability plus constraint problem, not a distributed variable one and so there is no maximization of entropy subject to a constraint involving the distributed variable. We note that ((9)) becomes the time-independent Schrodinger equation if one replaces $p^2/2m$ with $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$ and that E_n then takes on discrete values.

Distributed Variable Associated with Quantum Excitations

In the above section, we argued that a quantum bound state is based on a dynamical probability (square root flux) rather than maximization of entropy. What happens if one has a system in which a single bound particle jumps from one excited state to another by absorbing photons and decays, emitting photons. In this stochastic process, energy is conserved and is also the stochastic distributed variable i.e. the bound state energy changes. Thus the distributed variable approach to statistical mechanics applies. One may then use $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as the unnormalized weight of the quantum single particle state e_i , even though this state itself is created using a different kind of statistical mechanics namely one based on dynamical probability not maximization of entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there are at least two very different kinds of statistical mechanics based on the variable involved in the stochastic process. If the variable is a distributed one (i.e. a scalar which adds), as in the case of energy in elastic collisions in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas or energy in the case of photons being absorbed or emitted from single particle excited quantum states, one uses the distributed variable approach. This approach implies that the probability $n(e_3)$ for one particle to have a distributed variable value e_3 is the same as the product probabilities $n(e_1)n(e_2)$ if $e_3=e_1+e_2$. Taking \ln of $n(e_3)=n(e_2)n(e_1)$ and linking with $e_3=e_1+e_2$ yields the form $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where C, T are constants. Thus the MB probability is a distributed variable result. This distributed variable approach may immediately be written in terms of a maximization provided the constraint uses the distributed variable i.e. $e_i n(e_i)$ i.e.

$$\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ is equivalent to: } \frac{d}{dn(e_i)} n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) - e_i n(e_i)/T = 0.$$

Finally $n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i))$ is of the form of Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln N$. Thus maximization of entropy subject to a "special" constraint ultimately follows from the distributed variable approach because otherwise one would not know otherwise what constraint to use. (There could be many different correct constraints.) The constraint must use the distributed variable itself (not a function of it).

We also conclude that the above distributed variable statistical approach is not the only one found in nature. In fact, in the classical world there exists reflection/refraction of light. This is a statistical process as a photon has a probability to reflect or refract, but its energy remains constant while momentum, a vector changes. Thus energy is not a distributed variable. $E=pc$ so the momentum of the incident, reflected and refracted photons differ i.e. $p, -p, p_2$, but p is a vector not a distributed variable. Thus there seems to be a dynamical balance which occurs. This balance has been shown to be based on the square root of flux/intensity which is linked with an eigenfunction of the generator associated with the dynamical motion. In the case of p momentum one uses the translation generator or $-id/dx$ and has the eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$. This is a completely different statistical approach from the distributed variable one.

If there exists a bound system for which \hbar/p is of the same order as the length, then instead of using Newton's approach one may consider a statistical ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ s based on $V(x)$ delivering stochastic impulse hits. Thus the stochasticity is linked with a dynamic variable p not a distributed one. There also exists a constraint, namely that average $KE = E - V(x)$. Combining the two yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation which allows one to solve for energy levels

. If a single particle absorbs photons and jumps from one level to another and then decays emitting photons, this stochastic process uses energy as a distributed variable and so the distributed variable statistics may be used i.e $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as the unnormalized probability to be in state e_i , even though this state itself is created using a completely different statistical approach, namely that using a dynamical $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus we argue for two different kinds of statistical approaches based on either a scalar distributed variable (equivalent to maximization of entropy subject to a "special" constraint i.e. one which uses the exact distributed variable) or a dynamical one associated with a wavelike interfering probability based on the eigenfunction of the generator associated with the dynamical variable which changes in the stochastic process.

References

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